

STUDENTS' VIEWS ON TELETEACHING IN THE ELECTRONIC INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING DEGREE

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Abstract

COVID-19 pandemic has brought an unprecedented situation in all areas of society in the heart of the 21st century. The university sector has been immersed in a sudden change to adapt with great haste to the new conditions of confinement, going from face-to-face to virtual teaching.

The degree in Industrial Electronics Engineering offered by University of Almería, all teaching has been carried out in a distance format because of the health crisis. This paper presents the opinion of the students on the methodology developed under these circumstances. This methodology has been based on the use of new technologies available within the University of Almería. The technologies were used as support for the campus-based learning, and nowadays, they have acquired great prominence in online teaching. The changes in methodologies for the online learning adaptation of the subjects were previously approved and published for the general interest of the students in their corresponding addendum. In the addendums, the changes in the theoretical and practical methodology of each subject are collected, as well as the assessment standards. The opinion of 103 students from three different subjects has been analyzed, one of them a 2nd grade core subject, Basic Electronics (66.99% students) and two 3rd grade compulsory subjects, Power Electronics (19.42% students) and Digital Electronics (13.59% students). Online surveys were implemented through the virtual classroom of the respective subjects. The surveys have considered virtual teaching within the field of theoretical as well as practical electronics and they have made possible the establishment of performance indicators such as the potentiality of the educational resource, the promotion of self-learning, didactic versatility, didactic difficulties, didactic efficiency and evaluation.

Most of the students disagree with the quality of all indicators, except for the one related to didactic difficulty. The opinion of second grade students is not clear, there are similar percentages between those who agree and those who do not. Third-year students present a general opinion on the didactic difficulty in theoretical questions of the subject. All opinions have also been analyzed by grade because they present different responses. Second-year students value the methodology used in the practical lessons more negatively, while third-year students are more concerned about the development of the theoretical methodology.

In the part referred to evaluation, 52.51% disagree with the system established. Third-year students show a general opinion in disagreement with the online assessment system. If these results are analyzed objectively, the percentages of passes, fails and absent students for the three subjects do not show significant differences in the last recent years. Therefore, the established online assessment methodology has not caused any changes in the rating of the students' performance.

To improve the opinion of the students surveyed, actions to promote the efficiency of virtual teaching should be considered in the next years. The evaluation criteria should also be revised to adapt them to the specific characteristics of virtual teaching. The number of students surveyed in future calls should be increased to gather more conclusive results and avoid possible misinterpretations.

Keywords: Covid-19, Industrial electronics engineering, online, teleteaching.

1 INTRODUCTION

Year 2020 will be marked in history by the pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2, also known as coronavirus disease (COVID-19) [1]. COVID-19 pandemic has brought an unprecedented situation in all areas of society as we know it, in the heart of the 21st century.

Measures contemplated in Royal Decree 463/2020, of March 14th, declaring the state of alarm in Spain, provided the suspension of face-to-face teaching activity [2]. The closure of all educational levels affected 91.3% of the total number of students enrolled in the world: more than 1,500 million people have been unable to attend their face-to-face classes, according to UNESCO [3].

At the university level, the suspension of face-to-face teaching activities caused that all activities were immediately transferred to an online format. From this moment on, all Spanish universities began to rapidly adapt their teaching methods to the new situation, which meant multiplying all efforts and starting to use new technological, methodological and computer resources in order to teach classes and serve students, since no professor was fully prepared for this new situation. The urgent transformation of the face-to-face classes to an online format has been carried out in a way that can be described as generally acceptable, although the measures taken have been adjusted to haste and not to proposals specifically designed from the very beginning to teach subjects with a completely online methodology [4]. This step has had to be faced by centers, professors and students to establish an emergency response, in which technology has allowed us to think that a different, more innovative and creative university learning is possible [5]. Although it has not been possible to plan or ensure that all those involved had the minimum technological means required, the necessary digital skills and attitudes prone to change, among some concerns. This emergency situation has revealed and magnified the existence of three gaps [6]:

1. An access gap related to having or not having access to electronic devices and / or internet connection.
2. A gap in use, related to the time of use and the quality of this, because there will be households that do have devices, but they are shared among family members.
3. A skills gap related to the digital skills of professors and students to properly use digital platforms for educational purposes and the ability to create or provide content and educational activities through them.

Apart from these three gaps, it must be added the problems and implications derived from the online assessment. The development of online educational programs have evolved notably in a short period of time, but it always needs to be supported by pedagogical models and advances in learning technologies, however, the evaluation or certification of learning remains one of its weak points [7]. Evaluation as a process consisting of the verification of the mere achievement of some objectives or knowledge [8], is a process of enormous complexity and it includes the evaluation of the behavior or the student body's performance. It is the expression that tries to show the degree of sufficiency or insufficiency of the knowledge, skills or abilities of the students as a result of the application of some type of tests, activities, exams or processes [9].

Health circumstances require that this evaluation had been carried out in an uncertain context regard to legal regulations on data protection and privacy rights of all those involved, in addition to the risk of organized attacks to the systems that support online teaching and assessment [10].

Methodologies developed to teach various electronics subjects in the Industrial Electronics Engineering degree, taken during 2019/2020 academic year at the University of Almería will be considered in this work. In addition, the opinion of the students who have taken these subjects with the established online modality will be carefully analyzed.

2 METHODOLOGY

The Industrial Electronics Engineering degree is taught at the University of Almería since 2010. It aims to serve the needs of Industry and Administration in the field of Industrial Electronics and Automation. This degree is distributed in 240 ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) credits, divided into four years. During the first and the second year, a basic training and common to the industrial branch is established, with a distribution of 60 ECTS. The other two years include a specific industrial electronics technology module (78 ECTS). Students must also complete 12 ECTS of business practices, and another 12 ECTS in a final degree project. In total, the degree is taught in 41 subjects, which 10 of them are basic, 25 are compulsory and 6 are optional. In this work, students of a basic subject of the second-year (Basic Electronics) and of 2 compulsory subjects of the third-year electronics branch (Digital Electronics and Power Electronics) were surveyed.

The health situation derived from the Covid-19 pandemic led to the establishment of non-face-to-face teaching in all subjects of the Engineering degree. This paper focuses on some subjects of the Electronics Technology area and it has been decided to use technologies already available at the university and as similar as possible to those usually used to support face-to-face teaching. This measure is considered important so that both professors and students feel as safe as possible in the new context of compulsory online teaching.

Professors responsible for the online subjects made and published a series of documents or addendums in which the necessary changes were specified, in order to adapt the contents and the subject's

assessments due to the state of alarm. These documents were reviewed and approved by a committee or commission of the degree, in charge of verifying the quality of teaching and guaranteeing the transparency of the changes in the transformation of face-to-face teaching into a non-face-to-face system [11]. These addendums reflect the maintenance of the temporality in the development of the subjects in terms of schedules, as well as the schedules of the professors' tutorials that are carried out in a non-face-to-face way, by means of emails or videoconferences, requesting an appointment in advance by e-mail. The tools used are those included in the instructions of the multimodality of the University of Almería [12], Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Tools for online teaching.

The accomplishment of the laboratory practices changes remarkably compared to face-to-face model, since the realization of the assembly practices in the electronics laboratories are suppressed. These practices are replaced by expanding the weight of the theoretical exercises and simulation problems by means of a specific electronic simulation software. Regarding to the assessment criteria, the students (in pairs) must make a report of each block of practices, which must have a grade higher than 5 to be considered a pass.

All reports are delivered by a member of the pair through a link enabled in the Blackboard platform, with a specific deadline previously set in the subject online calendar.

Assessment in an online evaluation process is a matter of enormous complexity and it is required to be distributed continuously throughout instruction / learning, rather than occurring only at specific moments [13]. So, the worst possible scenario in an online assessment is when it is only limited to the end of the process, thus it is more recommendable to maintain the continuous assessment just as it was carried out in these subjects in the traditional face-to-face methodology.

A continuous assessment is carried out through two different blocks of topics, which do not represent more than 50% of the total final grade. The online tests are synchronous and allow the evaluation of a group of students in a similar way to the face-to-face normal situation and with the advantage of consulting the professors any doubt that may arise from the interpretation of the exam in real time [14]. This option also allows to solve in real time the possible technical difficulties during the test and to model the exam length if necessary. This kind of continuous assessment in scenarios with few students and with models focused on professor-student interaction is perfectly approachable and admissible [15]. As the number of students grows, continuous assessment solutions are not as feasible, and technology considerations need to be increased to conduct online assessments [16]. In these kind of tests, theoretical contents are evaluated through objective questions. A large bank of questions or items are created and then, they are randomly selected to be answered in a short response time. With these two measures, the risks that books / websites can be used to search for the answers and that the group of students share among themselves the answers are minimized [17].

All these evaluations should be monitored, since different studies have been established that unsupervised exams have a greater potential risk of inappropriate ethical behavior or a rise in grades [18]. The remote monitoring systems used are called e-proctoring systems [19]. The use of these remote surveillance systems is conceived as an attempt to equalize the incidence of academic dishonesty between online and face-to-face assessment tests [20], although, as in the supervision of face-to-face exams, there is no perfect supervision method. The e-proctoring systems allow video and audio surveillance, using the technical means of the student such as the use of the camera of his device, the control of the computer and the identification of the person who performs the evaluation test, detecting impersonation in the beginning or throughout the examination. In addition, the solutions to the questions performed in the test have to be attached to the online platform before the time is up [21]. These tools allow the synchronous online performance of the exam by videoconference at the scheduled time indicated through the subject BlackBoard Collaborate platform. During the exam, the professor is accessible in case doubts may arise, using the individual chat to avoid distractions of the rest of the students. If considerations can affect more than one student, the group chat could be used. This tool

meets the key requirements of e-proctoring, such as being compatible with different browsers, adapting to languages such as English and Spanish, and being easy to use [22].

A screen appears before starting the test, with the instructions, a link leading to the questions, as well as a task where the students must attach the answers (pdf document).

In online teaching processes, it should be considered that students who enrolled in face-to-face studies do not have to have the necessary technological infrastructure to take the subjects and their assessments in an online format. Although technological penetration is wide, viable solutions are proposed to these students (such as temporary loan of laptops, data cards and Wi-Fi routers). It should also be considered that during the tests through the virtual campus with the basic level of identification and with a limited time, there is a possibility that the system may not respond, and students will not be able to take the full exam. In subjects with many enrolled students (the case with the common subject of the second year), in order to avoid large confluences, the test was carried out in groups, proposing equivalent but different tests to each group. Because of this, a large questions bank had to be created. In all cases, the time to complete the test is limited and a schedule is planned for the performance of each part of the test. There is the option of repeating the test by individual videoconference if the student's connection drops for an extended period of time, and no alternative can be given such as lengthening the time to compensate for the time without connection [23].

It is of crucial important to know the weaknesses and strengths of the system that was carried out during this year. To this end, an online survey was created, where the basic aspects of the methodology followed are collected. This survey is carried out asynchronously by the students who have taken these subjects this year, once the semester is over. The objective of this survey is to achieve an effective orientation-learning process, considering aspects such as planning, organization, direction, control and assessment of the subject in online scenarios.

Table 1 shows the survey to evaluate the results of online teaching through 19 questions. Different levels of satisfaction are considered, as well as the possibility that the students do not answer.

Table 1. Questionnaire tele-education applied to practical concepts in working groups from students of Industrial Electronics Engineering. Indicator rating levels: 1= Totally agree, 2= Agreed, 3= Neither agree nor disagree, 4= Disagree, 5= Totally disagree, 6= Not applicable, No answer.

Indicator: Tele-education applied to theoretical concepts in teaching groups	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Enough material has been added to acquire the knowledge of the subject.						
2. The evaluation criteria have been adapted to the new teaching framework.						
3. Enough means have been used to solve theoretical doubts in an efficient way.						
4. The methodology used has allowed the progressive acquisition of the contents.						
5. The virtual teaching has allowed a better planning of the time available for the learning of the contents.						
6. Difficulties have arisen in the temporal planning of the subject.						
7. There have been difficulties in the monitoring of the subject for reasons beyond the teacher's control.						
8. The telematic context implies greater ease of learning than face-to-face classes.						
9. I consider the teacher's involvement in virtual teaching to be enough.						
10. The difficulty to pass the subject has increased due to the new circumstances.						
Indicator: Tele-education applied to practical concepts in working groups	1	2	3	4	5	6
11. The simulator has facilitated the task of virtual learning to consolidate theoretical concepts.						
12. The practical activities proposed have facilitated the monitoring of the theoretical explanations.						
13. The lack of interaction in the laboratory environment has been replaced as far as possible by means of simulation practices in terms of the knowledge acquired.						
14. The interaction with the teaching staff in the virtual teaching has been enough to acquire the necessary practical knowledge.						
15. The means used by the teaching staff have been enough for the resolution of the proposed practical exercises.						
16. Doubts regarding the simulator and the efficient performance of the practices have been resolved.						
17. The simulation program allows the development of a good professional practice.						
18. The use of virtual instruments brings the virtual laboratory closer to the real one.						
19. Virtual teaching cannot replace practical learning in electronics subjects.						

In this survey, 6 different indicators applied to the development of theory and practices have been evaluated (Table 2).

Table 2. Indicator-questionnaire relationship.

Indicator \ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	
Potential of the educational resource																				
Promotion of self-learning																				
Teaching versatility																				
Teaching efficiency																				

traditional method during their learning process. Most of the more experienced students prefer the resolution of doubts during the class, and tutorials for the resolution of specific questions. The second-year subject supposes the first approach to electronics for the students and due to the circumstances of this year, they have only been able to attend one face-to-face class. This has not allowed them to adequately appreciate the difference between face-to-face and virtual classes. These last students consider the virtual laboratory as a good aid for the practices and not so much for theory. During this one-year course, it has also been implemented a series of theory-practice questionnaires that they had to take before in order to access to the practices, which have helped them to acquire a better knowledge, although they have had to spend extra time to take them. These questionnaires were not implemented for the third-year students, since they already had a good knowledge in the simulator and in the traditional measurement systems existing in laboratories.

The representation of the “Teaching versatility” indicator is shown in Figure 3a. It is based on two questions, 5 and 8, to assess planning and ease of learning with virtual teaching. 47.39% of students do not agree that this methodology improves these two issues compared to 19.11% who positively value virtual teaching. There is 22.47% of students who neither agree nor disagree and 11.04% do not answer the questions. The second-year students value positively a better planning of the time available for learning and they are the ones who do not answer this question, while third-year students value the ease of learning compared to face-to-face classes and they do not agree that it helps with planning.

Figure 3. Representation in percentage: a) The Teaching Versatility, b) The Teaching difficulties.

Figure 3b represents the “Teaching difficulties” indicator. It is based on five questions to try to assess the difficulties of getting the new system up and acquiring theoretical-practical knowledge in virtual teaching. 47.72% of the students agree with the existence of difficulties to follow the subject (question 6), difficulties beyond the professor’s control (question 7) and difficulties to pass the subject due to the new circumstances (question 10), and inconveniences of the means used to solve practical exercises (question 15), as well as the performance of the practices in an efficient way (question 16). 16.28% of the students disagree that there are difficulties, being the second-year students who have contributed the most to this percentage. There is 22.48% of students who do not neither agree or disagree and 13.04% who do not answer these questions. Furthermore, these second-year students are more divided between those who consider that there are difficulties and those who do not. The third-year students are supportive of the fact that there are difficulties in following the subject and these difficulties are beyond the professor’s control in matters of theory. They also present fewer inconveniences in the means used and in the resolution of doubts regarding the simulator in the practices. As mentioned above, these students have an advanced level in the use of the simulator because they used it in the previous year, so they do not appreciate difficulties in practical matters, although they do in theoretical ones.

The “Teaching efficiency” indicator is represented in Figure 4a. This indicator is based on four questions, one to assess the professor’s involvement in theoretical virtual teaching (question 9) and three questions to assess the practices, related to issues such as the use of the simulator to consolidate theoretical concepts, practical activities to monitor theoretical explanations and whether the interaction with the teaching staff in virtual teaching has been sufficient to acquire the necessary practical knowledge (questions 11, 12 and 14). The answers to question 9 present the greatest discrepancies among all students, 34.44% disagree with the efficiency of this methodology in the three subjects studied and 32.18% agree or totally agree on didactic efficiency. Again, the students of the three subjects have a similar opinion. Students are divided between those who value didactic efficiency and those who do not, although there is a high percentage who do not respond (17.37%) and others who do not know how to assess this fact (15.41%). This issue must be worked in depth in the future, in order to obtain conclusive results.

The last indicator refers to the evaluation process and it is the one that presents the most controversy within the university community. On this occasion, only one question has been used (question 2) and it allows evaluating the virtual evaluation by means of the statement: "The evaluation criteria have been adapted to the new teaching framework." Figure 4b shows that there is a majority assessment of disagreement with 52.51% of the students, compared to 10.58% of students who agreed. The students of third-year subjects are the ones who disagree the most and the second-year students are the ones who agree more. There is a high percentage who do not think either in favor or against, or do not respond in this regard (36.92%). This question is always controversial, since only students who have passed the subject value it well and students who have failed usually blame the established evaluation criteria for it.

Figure 4. Representation in percentage: a) The Teaching efficiency, b) The Evaluation.

The last indicator refers to the evaluation process and it is the one that presents the most controversy within the university community. On this occasion, only one question has been used (question 2) and it allows evaluating the virtual evaluation by means of the statement: "The evaluation criteria have been adapted to the new teaching framework." Figure 7 shows that there is a majority assessment of disagreement with 52.51% of the students, compared to 10.58% of students who agreed. The students of third-year subjects are the ones who disagree the most and the second-year students are the ones who agree more. There is a high percentage who do not think either in favor or against, or do not respond in this regard (36.92%). This question is always controversial, since only students who have passed the subject value it well and students who have failed usually blame the established evaluation criteria for it.

To verify objectively the followed methodology, the grades obtained during this year are compared with those obtained in the past years, where the same continuous assessment criteria were applied, but in the traditional face-to-face way. These results are analyzed by subject and represented in Figures 8-10.

In the Basic Electronics subject, there are pass and fail results like those of the last three years (Figure 5a). There is a significant difference in the 2013-14 to 2015-16 academic years. Although the continuous assessment criteria have been the same, students who joined engineering these years were students with a higher GPA (Grade Point Average), which leads to a greater number of passes, even though the number of fails is also higher and the number of absent was very small. In the last four years there is a large number of absent students because in the continuous assessment system, if the student does not take the last evaluation test he is marked as absent, and most of these students pass in the extraordinary evaluation session.

Figure 5. Representation in percentage of the time evolution of June's ordinary evaluation session: a) The Basic Electronics subject, b) The Digital Electronics subject.

Figure 5b shows the grades evolution for the Digital Electronics subject. The results obtained from this year within the virtual teaching model are similar to those obtained last year and the 2016-17 academic year and with the same trend as the results of Basic Electronics students in recent years (similar continuous assessment methodology).

Figure 6 shows the grades evolution for the Power Electronics subject. The results obtained from this year within the virtual teaching model are better than those obtained in the last three years. The number of passes has decreased since the 2016-17 academic year as the complexity of the practices have increased, which are changed annually. Until these changes in the practices took place, there were a large number of students who cheated on the practices and they copied the practices of the previous year.

In the light of the results of the three subjects, it does not appear that there is a significant increase in the number of passes or fails due to the methodology established during this year. Despite the wide range in the opinion of the students, the numbers of passes, fails and absent are the same in the three subjects studied in this work. Therefore, there are no significant differences in the performance of the subjects due to the new non-face-to-face modality.

Figure 6. Representation in percentage of the time evolution of June's ordinary evaluation session for the Power Electronics subject.

4 CONCLUSIONS

COVID-19 pandemic has brought an unprecedented situation in all areas of educational, economic and social activity. The state of alarm and the subsequent lockdown order has affected all educational levels. Despite this, every crisis leaves some positive elements, and COVID-19 pandemic has caused a deep reflection in all educational designs at all levels. Specifically, in the case of the university field, a true digital transformation has been developed to make the best use of the digital and non-face-to-face potentialities of teaching.

After the experience carried out, and considering the opinions of the students, the importance of an adequate methodology for virtual teaching can be extracted in a general way. Although there is a large number of students who positively value the advantages of virtualization, a greater number consider this virtualization as a support and not as a unique alternative.

Virtual laboratories are established as a support tool for the correct acquisition of professional skills for an electronics engineer. The virtual laboratory should be used progressively from the first year until reaching a maximum value at the end of the degree. This fact is evident in the opinion of the third-year students. Students must be prepared for the professional environment that they will find, acquiring specific skills, so a proper use of the virtual laboratory must be established without setting aside the advantages that the face-to-face laboratory provides.

In this work, the opinion of the students of three subjects of the Degree in Industrial Electronics Engineering taken virtually at the University of Almeria has been considered to evaluate the adaptation of the students to the changes derived from the COVID-19 pandemic. 103 students were surveyed, distributed as follows: 69 Basic Electronics students, 24 Digital Electronics students and 20 Power Electronics students. This survey has considered virtual teaching within the field of electronics and it take into account indicators that include concepts such as the potential of the didactic resource, promotion of self-learning, didactic versatility, didactic difficulties, didactic efficiency and evaluation. The total number of indicators is 6, which have also been related to the theoretical and practical knowledge of the subject. The opinion of the students differs according the grade, showing greater concern in the methodology of the practices for the second-year students, while the students of third-year show a greater concern in the methodology of the theoretical lessons. Most of the indicators have been valued in disagreement, so almost all students do not consider that the online methodologies established in the

Industrial Electronics Engineering degree are enough for an adequate learning. The evaluations of the questions and the grades have been analyzed, and the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Regarding the potential of the didactic resource, it can be considered that the use of the virtual laboratory instead the traditional laboratory practices is not the best solution to establish a proper training. This is the common opinion of the teacher staff involved in these subjects, who consider the use of virtual laboratories as a reinforcement tool and not as an exclusive learning method.
- About the promotion of self-learning, second-year students are more dissatisfied with issues related to the development of practices, while third-year students are more dissatisfied with the theoretical methodology. This difference could be attributed to the fact that third-year students were already familiar with the use of the virtual tools, but not in a theoretical level.
- Regarding the didactic versatility, the second-year students value more satisfactorily the planning of the time available for learning and the third-year students establish a better opinion of the ease of learning through online methodologies.
- Most students agree that there are great didactic difficulties with the online methodology. Second-year students are divided between those who consider the existence of difficulties and those who do not appreciate them as such. Almost all third-year students do not appreciate difficulties in practical matters, but they do in theoretical matters.
- Regarding the concept of didactic efficiency, there are no significant differences in the opinions of the students of the three subjects.
- About the evaluation topics, third-year students show a majority opinion in disagreement with the online assessment system. If these results are objectively analyzed, the percentages of pass, fail and absent of the three subjects do not show significant differences during the last years. Therefore, the established assessment methodology does not propose modifications regarding the assessment of student performance. If these results are objectively analyzed, the percentages of pass, fail and fail of the three subjects do not show significant differences during the last years. Therefore, the established evaluation methodology does not affect the students' performance.

In order to improve the feedback received, actions to increase or promote the use of virtual teaching should be considered. The first action to be carried out is an adequate planning of the subjects, which requires resources and time for its implementation. In addition, through improved simulation tools, the applicability and promotion of learning can be increased, and a wide variety of lecture methods can be studied to check which ones are best for the acquisition of knowledge by students. A concept that should be studied in depth is the adaptation of the evaluation criteria to the specific characteristics of non-face-to-face methodology, trying to make the students feel involved and motivated during the entire evaluation process. They have to feel sure about the potential of the evaluation tools, with objective tests similar to those carried out in the traditional face-to-face environment. All these actions must be focused on trying to obtain more conclusive results in the future. In addition, the sample of students surveyed must be increased, to avoid possible misinterpretations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] U. Maggiore *et al.*, "How should I manage immunosuppression in a kidney transplant patient with COVID-19? An ERA-EDTA DESCARTES expert opinion," *Nephrol. Dial. Transplant.*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 899–904, 2020.
- [2] G. de España, "Real Decreto 463/2020, de 14 de marzo, por el que se declara el estado de alarma para la gestión de la situación de crisis sanitaria ocasionada por el COVID-19," *Boletín Oficial del Estado*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://bit.ly/3bZDDnD>.
- [3] Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia, "Real Decreto 1393/2007 , de 29 de octubre , por el que se establece la ordenación de las enseñanzas universitarias oficiales," *Real Decreto*, vol. BOE núm. 2, no. de 30 de octubre de 2007, pp. 1–25, 2007.
- [4] C. Hodges, S. Moore, B. Lockee, T. Trust, and A. Bond, "The Difference Between Emergency

- Remote Teaching and Online Learning,” *Educ. Rev.*, 2020.
- [5] I. Segura Moreno, “La Crisis Sistemática provocada por el Covid-19 y su impacto en la Universidad,” *Aula Encuentro*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 1–4, 2020.
- [6] F. J. García-Peñalvo, “Modelo de referencia para la enseñanza no presencial en universidades presenciales,” *Campus Virtuales*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 2020, 2020.
- [7] M. Gil Rivera, “Modelo de diseño instruccional para programas educativos a distancia,” *Perfiles Educ.*, vol. 26, no. 104, pp. 93–114, 2004.
- [8] R. W. Tyler, *Basic principles of curriculum construction*, vol. 52, no. 12. 1952.
- [9] C. A. S.. and J. Cabrerizo Diago, *Evaluacion educativa de aprendizajes y competencias*, Pearson. Madrid, España, 2010.
- [10] F. J. García-Peñalvo, A. Corell, V. Abella-García, and M. Grande, “La evaluación online en la educación superior en tiempos de la COVID-19,” *Educ. Knowl. Soc.*, vol. 21, no. 0, p. 26, 2020.
- [11] *Recomendaciones sobre criterios generales para la adaptación del sistema universitario español ante la pandemia del Covid-19, durante el curso 2019-2020*. 2020.
- [12] J. Politis and D. Politis, “The relationship between an online synchronous learning environment and knowledge acquisition skills and traits: The blackboard collaborate experience,” *Electron. J. e-Learning*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 196–222, 2016.
- [13] A. M. Seoane Pardo and F. J. García Peñalvo, “Determining Quality for Online Activities. Methodology and Training of Online Tutors as a Challenge for Achieving the Excellence,” *WSEAS Trans. Adv. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 3, no. 9, pp. 823–830, 2006.
- [14] A. M. Seoane-Pardo and F. J. García-Peñalvo, “Pedagogical patterns and online teaching,” *Online Tutor 2.0 Methodol. Case Stud. Success. Learn.*, pp. 298–316, 2014.
- [15] A. M. Seoane Pardo and F. J. García Peñalvo, “Philosophical and epistemological basis for building a quality online training methodology,” *Adv. E-Learning Exp. Methodol.*, pp. 46–60, 2008.
- [16] A. E. Fluck, “An international review of eExam technologies and impact,” *Comput. Educ.*, vol. 132, no. December 2018, pp. 1–15, 2019.
- [17] B. K. Pathak, “Emerging online educational models and the transformation of traditional universities,” *Electron. Mark.*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 315–321, 2016.
- [18] J. Carstairs and B. Myors, “Internet testing: A natural experiment reveals test score inflation on a high-stakes, unproctored cognitive test,” *Comput. Human Behav.*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 738–742, 2009.
- [19] D. J. Prince, R. A. Fulton, and T. W. Garsombke, “Comparisons Of Proctored Versus Non-Proctored Testing Strategies In Graduate Distance Education Curriculum,” *J. Coll. Teach. Learn.*, vol. 6, no. 7, pp. 51–62, 2009.
- [20] O. R. Harmon and J. Lambrinos, “Are online exams an invitation to cheat?,” *J. Econ. Educ.*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 116–125, 2008.
- [21] Fidalgo-Blanco Ángel, Léis Dolores, Sein-Echaluce María Luisa, and F. J. García-Peñalvo, “Monitoring Indicators for CTMTC: Comprehensive Training Model of the Teamwork Competence in Engineering Domain,” *Int. J. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 829–823, 2015.
- [22] C. S. González-González, A. Infante-Moro, and J. C. Infante-Moro, “Implementation of e-proctoring in online teaching: A study about motivational factors,” *Sustain.*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 1–13, 2020.
- [23] T. Luo, A. Murray, and H. Crompton, “International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning Designing Authentic Learning Activities to Train Pre-Service Teachers About Teaching Online Designing Authentic Learning Activities to Train Pre- Service Teachers About Teaching Online,” *Int. Rev. Res. Open Distrib. Learn.*, vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 141–157, 2020.